

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF THE EFFECT OF UV RADIATION AND SALT WATER ON THE DYNAMIC PROPERTIES AND FAILURE OF CARBON FIBER-VINYLESTER COMPOSITES

M. Alkhader^{1*}, C. Korach¹, F.P. Chiang¹

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Stony Brook University, Stony Brook, USA

* Corresponding author (maen.alkhader@stonybrook.edu)

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1. Introduction

Advanced materials in the form of composites have become increasingly used in a wide range of applications from aerospace and automotive industries to transportation systems, civil engineering and wind energy technologies. The appeal of composite materials has stemmed mostly from their high strength, stiffness and low density, allowing them to provide substantial weight reduction when compared to monolithic materials. Moreover, composite materials offer additional appealing properties such as better corrosion resistance over traditional metallic materials [1]; efficient candidates for the development and repair of new and deteriorating structures; repairability, long-term cost effectiveness, formability into complex forms with limited need to machining; and customizability through varying composite materials' constituents as well as their ratios, geometries, and arrangements. Customizability and tunability of composites have already been utilized to create composites with a wide range of controlled and designed properties such as ductility, fatigue resistance, controlled anisotropy, capacity to absorb impact energy and corrosion resistance. The aforementioned properties offered by composites motivated naval, infrastructure and structural applications that have traditionally relied on steel, aluminum and concrete to move toward using polymer based composites as primary or secondary load bearing components.

Although, polymer based composites have shown great potential as candidates in naval, structural and infrastructural applications, there remain some

important lingering questions regarding their long-term mechanical properties, durability and structural integrity. Answering these questions is, not only, important for reaching a better understanding of these materials long-term mechanical properties, but also, is instrumental for their wide-spread implementation; particularly, in critical applications. The uncertainties associated with composites long-term durability are linked to a multitude of conditions that composite materials can be exposed to and adversely affected by in real life applications [2]. For example, the effect of environmental exposure (humidity) was observed to cause detrimental effects on long-term residual mechanical properties of vinyl ester resin composites [3]. Often, fiber reinforced composites are exposed to aggressive environments, which include: ultraviolet radiation, humidity, salt water, mechanical stresses and temperature fluctuations. With time, such harsh environments can degrade the mechanical properties of fiber reinforced polymer based composites by changing the physical and/or chemical properties of matrix, fibers and matrix-fiber interface strength characteristics [4, 5] through various mechanisms. More importantly, the adverse effect of environmental elements was observed to be amplified when they act in a combined manner [6]. For example, humidity, temperature and moisture can cause degradation through plasticization, hydrolysis, fiber-matrix debonding and microcracking due to temperature ageing and water ingress [7]. Another environmental element that is abundantly available is UV radiation stemming from sun light. Exposure to UV radiation can lead to reduction in strength [6, 8, 9]; increased creep strain

[6, 9]; result in surface cracking that can lead to stress concentration and reduction in strength [10]. In addition, the deterioration due to UV light was observed to be increased when UV radiation was combined with moisture [6, 9].

Environmental degradation can detrimentally affect a wide range of mechanical properties such as long-term stiffness, strength, fracture and failure behavior in both the quasi-static and dynamic regimes. The effect of long-term exposure to harsh environments on the dynamic properties is particularly relevant to infrastructure, aerospace and naval applications where composites might be subjected to slamming, impact and shock loading. The latter pertains to applications with military functions or serving in conflict zones where composites might be exposed to projectiles and explosions.

Significant efforts have been directed at quantifying the effect of harsh environments on the long-term mechanical properties and failure of fiber reinforced composites; however, this remains a research topic since the wide range of materials, environmental parameters and exposure periods involved create a very large parameter space that needs to be investigated. More importantly, experimental simulation of long term exposure to environmental elements can be very time consuming since specimens should be exposed to environmental elements in controlled environments for extended periods of time (probably months if not years).

Most of the previous efforts to characterize the effect of environmental variables on the long term mechanical properties of composites were directed at the effect of harsh environments on the quasi-static properties. On the other hand, environmental degradation effect on dynamic properties of polymer fiber reinforced composites is not well investigated or characterized. With composites being increasingly incorporated in aerospace and naval applications, the effect of environmental elements on the long term durability of composites under dynamic loading becomes important. Accordingly this work aims to quantify the effect of extended exposure to UV radiation and salt water on the high-strain-rate properties and dynamic failure of carbon fiber-reinforced vinylester composites. This composite system is widely used in naval applications and, therefore, can be anticipated to be exposed to UV radiation, sea water, slamming loads and impact loadings. Extended exposure to these environmental parameters may cause failure to occur

at loadings significantly lower than the observed ones during laboratory testing using pristine specimens. Failure includes fracture, break, excessive deformation and/or unstable deformation due to loss of stiffness, or simply loss of functionality. However, this work emphasizes on failure in terms of fracture or loss of load carrying capacity.

2. Experimental

2.1 Specimens

Specimens were obtained from an external vendor (www.graphitestore.com) in the form of unidirectional carbon fiber laminates (24" wide and 36" height). Laminates are made from 33 m.s.i. Carbon and Vinylester epoxy. Strength data provided by the vendor shows that the laminates have a tensile strength of 2.69 GPa and bending strength of 1.875 GPa. Specimens were cut from the composite laminates using a shear press. Specimens have a nominal width of 13mm and length between (60 to 76mm). Specimens were prepared to investigate the effect of environment on the mechanical properties along the 0 direction (fiber direction); therefore, all specimens were cut such that the fibers were aligned with specimens' length.

2.2 Environmental exposure

To simulate the effect of environment, specimens representing the composite are first aged in controlled environment using the environmental exposure chambers shown in Fig.1.

The QUV/se accelerated weathering chamber is used to expose specimens to controlled levels of UV radiation, condensation/humidity, and combined levels of UV radiation/condensation. UV radiation simulates sunlight as the chamber utilizes fluorescent UV bulbs at a 340nm wavelength. During the aging process the UV intensity will be monitored by real-time UV irradiance sensors, while temperature can be controlled using a built-in blower. To simulate the effect of combined exposure to UV light and sea water, specimens were immersed in a tank of sea water and then the tank was placed in the UV weathering chamber. Combined exposure to UV light and sea water is most relevant to composites used in or near sea water (marine vessels, bridges, naval structures). Although the process of simulating exposure to environmental parameters is straightforward, the process is very time consuming as specimens have to be placed in the chamber for extended period of time (months and years). Therefore, this paper is

focused on the effect of three months of combined exposure to UV light-sea water.

Testing of aged specimens will allow determining the effect of aging conditions on the failure properties of vinylester carbon fiber composites under dynamic loading.

2.3 Dynamic tests

Dynamic high-strain-rates tests are performed using a single bar customized Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) apparatus. This apparatus has a gas gun (capacity 300 psi) and 8' long impact resistant polycarbonate bar with a diameter of 0.75". The Polycarbonate bar was acquired from (www.mcmaster.com) and has an elastic modulus of 2.5 GPa. Dynamic tests are performed using a 3-point bend arrangement. Schematics of the test are illustrated in Fig. 2. At the tip of the bar a steel cylinder of 1/8" diameter is placed to ensure that the loading is close to a point load and to protect the polycarbonate bar. In few early attempts, the end of the polycarbonate bar was machined into a tip of 1/8" diameter; however, the tip was permanently deformed and chipped during tests. Accordingly, the steel tip was used. Multiple strikers were fabricated but the 6" striker was used in these tests as it generated a stress pulse long enough to break tested specimens. During tests the striker of pre-designed length is propelled by the gas gun. The striker hits the incident bar and generates a stress wave that travels across the bar and partially reflects off the end touching specimen. Both the incident and reflected stress signals are registered using a strain gage and recorded using an oscilloscope (Lecroy WaveAce 2004). Registered strain data are used to compute the force acting on the specimen during the test which will be referred to as incident force. A high speed camera (Photron SA 1.1) is used in conjunction with this test to monitor the deformation and capture images at a rate of 67000 frames per second, equivalent to frame every 15 micro second. The oscilloscope is used to trigger the camera once the incident strain signal arrives at the strain gage. High speed images are used to pinpoint the onset of failure, investigate the deformation mode, and deduce the curvature and deformation history of tested specimens. Pictures of the actual setup and three point bend support fixture are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4

During experiments tested specimens are assumed in dynamic equilibrium, and thus, inertia forces are ignored, assuming they are negligibly small. To verify this assumption a finite element model that

includes the striker, bar, specimen and support was created using ABAQUS. Dimensions of the parts in the model was identical the actual dimensions. Picture of the finite element model is shown in Fig. 5. This model employed symmetry boundary conditions to reduce the problem size, therefore, only one quarter of the actual problem was modeled. Simulation showed that inertia force can be ignored and that the force acting on each support is equal to half of the force applied by the bar. Dynamic equilibrium was established easily mostly since the loading pulse has a very long rise time. Loading pulse is the strain pulse generated due to the impact of the sticker with the incident bar. An example of a loading pulse is illustrated in Fig. 6, which shows the pulse generated by impacting the incident bar with a striker flying at 18m/s. The pulse has a rise time of 200 micro seconds which is long enough for sound waves to reverberate in the specimen and achieve dynamic equilibrium.

3. Results

During tests the incident bar tip and the specimen/bar interface would move following a velocity profile similar to the one shown in Fig. 7. The velocity increases almost linearly until it plateaus and then decreases almost linearly. If the loaded structure or specimen in this case loses its load carrying capacity the velocity profile will show a kink followed by velocity increase. Velocity increases as specimen loses its capacity to resist the motion of the bar. This kink or the onset of failure is marked with a circle in Fig.7. Although, in this example pinpointing the kink is easy, there is always a need to confirm that this kink is caused by failure. This is achieved by the high speed camera. Images illustrating the deformation process are captured during our test every 15 micro seconds, therefore, the onset of failure can be pinpointed within 15 micro seconds accuracy. Fig. 8 shows sequence of images captured near the onset of failure for specimens impacted with a velocity of 18 m/s. The first image (top left corner) shows the specimen before loading, while the last three images are taken at 15 micro seconds intervals near the onset of failure. At this rate, the image resolution is 256 by 256 pixels which is not enough to resolve the small details in the fracture zone; however, the images can be used to compute the curvature and deduce the failure mode and most importantly pinpoint the moment of failure.

It should be noted that the specimen length to thickness ratio is 27 and therefore transverse shear stress effect on failure can be ignored. Moreover, failure was observed to occur, in all tests included in this paper, at the midpoint and failed specimens exhibited matching surfaced along the fractured surfaces.

The force at the bar tip-specimen interface can be computed from the measured strain signals (incident and reflected). Since the incident pulse is compressive and the reflected is tensile, the incident force is the difference between them and it is always compressive. The incident force of the specimen shown in Fig. 8 is plotted in Fig. 9 against the displacement, which is intern computed by integrating the velocity profile shown in Fig. 7. This figure shows that the force required to break the specimen is around 600 N which is very small and this is why polycarbonate bars are used. Similar force acting on aluminum or other metal bars would generate very small strains that can be extremely difficult to register using strain gages. Polycarbonate has a modulus of 2.5 GPa which is about 30 times smaller than the modulus of aluminum and therefore, for the same force, polycarbonate would exhibit 30 times larger strains. The drawback of using polycarbonate is that it breaks or yields at stress around 60 MPa; therefore, to reach higher loading velocities, other bars should be used.

One can introduce few simplifying assumptions at this point. First, the modulus of this composite is not very sensitive to the environmental elements: UV light and sea water. Second, the modulus is not sensitive to the loading rate achieved in this work. Third, simple linear beam theory can be applied. The first assumption was verified by the authors in a related work on the same composite but under quasi-static loading. The second assumption can be considered valid since the strain rates achieved in this work do not exceed 110 s^{-1} . The third assumption is also valid since the composite specimens failed in brittle manner without showing and significant plasticity. The invoked assumptions permit using simple beam theory to compute the strain and stress at the outmost surface of the specimen and opposite to the loading point (i.e. max tensile stress and strain). These quantities are needed to enable comparing results to known values in literature and among results from specimens with different dimensions. Thickness of our specimens varied between 1.35mm to 1.5 mm, and therefore, max stress values are need to construct comparisons

and form conclusions. It should be noted that the carbon fiber laminate acquired and used to prepare the specimens had a varying thickness, which led to having specimens with different thicknesses.

Using simple beam theory the maximum stress and strain were computed for the specimen shown in Fig.8. The maximum stress vs. displacement response is presented in Fig. 10, while the strain rate vs displacement is shown if Fig. 11. It should be noted that beyond the point of fracture the strain rate data and stress data are not valid. So beyond the 3mm point the data should be discarded. From Fig. 11 one can see that the maximum strain rate is about 100 s^{-1} even though the test is employed 18 m/s impact velocity. To reach strain rates of more than 1000 s^{-1} velocities of more than 180 m/s are needed and polycarbonate bars cannot deliver such velocities. Figs. 10 and 11 shows that the specimen shown in Fig. 8 has flexure strength of ($\sim 1.8 \text{ GPa}$) at 100 s^{-1} strain rate.

The aforementioned analysis has been repeated on all tested specimens and the flexure strength data was obtained for specimens exposed to UV light\sea water and for as received specimens. Results are presented in Fig.12.

Fig. 12 shows slight strain rate sensitivity and a drop in strength values due to the combined exposure to UV light and sea water. The reduction in strength can be attributed to slight deterioration in matrix properties or matrix-fiber bonding strength due to exposure to sea water and UV light. The measured drop resulted from three months long exposure to UV light and sea water. It is quite possible that the effect might increase if the exposure period is longer and therefore more tests will follow. Moreover, much larger number of specimens should be tested to minimize the effect of data scatter.

4. Conclusions

Three point bend dynamic tests were performed on unidirectional carbon fiber vinylester composite. Two sets of specimens were tested: one as receive, while the other was exposed to UV light and sea water for a period of three months. Results show some deterioration in the flexure strength due to the exposure to UV light and sea water. To place the results in the right perspective, more tests should be performed and specimens should be subjected to longer exposure periods. The new test will shed light on the susceptibility of these composites to exhibit further deterioration in the properties which if true

might threaten the long term durability of marine vehicles made of similar composites.

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Fig. 1. Environmental exposure performed in the laboratory with accelerated aging chambers, showing the QUV/se ultraviolet radiation and condensation chamber. More details about the utilization of this tool can be found in [1]

Fig. 2. Schematics of the dynamic testing configuration

Fig. 3. Left: Picture of the modified split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB), showing the gas gun, bar arrangement and data acquisition system. Right: the fixture with adjustable supports which is used in the dynamic three point-bend experiments (modified SHPB). Specimen sits between the fixture and the incident bar.

Fig. 4. Showing the loaded specimen, high speed camera and lighting system.

Fig. 5. Finite element model of the experimental setup

Fig. 6. Loading pulse generated after impacting a striker moving at around 18 m/s with the bar. The pulse was recorded after traversing 4' span of the bar and exhibits a relatively long ramp (200 micro second rise time).

